

A NOTE ON BOOLEAN LATTICES AND FAREY SEQUENCES

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Abstract

We establish monotone bijections between the Farey sequences of order m and the half-sequences of Farey subsequences associated with the rank m elements of the Boolean lattice of subsets of a $2m$ -set. We also present a few related combinatorial identities.

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1. Introduction

The *Farey sequence of order n* , denoted by \mathcal{F}_n , is the ascending sequence of irreducible fractions $\frac{h}{k} \in \mathbb{Q}$ with $0 \leq h \leq k \leq n$, see, e.g., [2, Chapter 27], [3, §3], [4, Chapter 4], [5, Chapter III], [8, Chapter 6], [9, Chapter 5]; their numerators and denominators are presented in sequences A006842 and A006843 in Sloane's *On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences*. For example, $\mathcal{F}_6 = \left(\frac{0}{1} < \frac{1}{6} < \frac{1}{5} < \frac{1}{4} < \frac{1}{3} < \frac{2}{5} < \frac{1}{2} < \frac{3}{5} < \frac{2}{3} < \frac{3}{4} < \frac{4}{5} < \frac{5}{6} < \frac{1}{1}\right)$.

For any integer m , $0 < m < n$, the ascending sets

$$\left(\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}_n : h \leq m\right) \tag{1}$$

are interesting Farey subsequences [1].

Let C be a finite set of cardinality $n := |C|$ greater than or equal to two, and A its proper subset; $m := |A|$. Denote the Boolean lattice of subsets of C by $\mathbb{B}(n)$; the empty set is denoted by $\hat{0}$, and the family of l -element subsets of C is denoted by $\mathbb{B}(n)^{(l)}$. Let $\gcd(\cdot, \cdot)$ denote the greatest common divisor of two integers. The ascending sequence of fractions

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), m) &:= \left(\frac{|B \cap A|}{\gcd(|B \cap A|, |B|)} / \frac{|B|}{\gcd(|B \cap A|, |B|)} : B \subseteq C, |B| > 0\right) \\ &= \left(\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}_n : h \leq m, k - h \leq n - m\right), \end{aligned}$$

considered in [7], has the properties very similar to those of the standard Farey sequence \mathcal{F}_n and of Farey subsequence (1).

The Farey subsequences $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) := (\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}_{2m} : h \leq m, k - h \leq m)$ arise in analysis of decision-making problems [6]. One such subsequence is

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(12), 6) = (\frac{0}{1} < \frac{1}{7} < \frac{1}{6} < \frac{1}{5} < \frac{1}{4} < \frac{2}{7} < \frac{1}{3} < \frac{3}{8} < \frac{2}{5} < \frac{3}{7} < \frac{4}{9} < \frac{5}{11} < \frac{1}{2} < \frac{6}{11} < \frac{5}{9} < \frac{4}{7} < \frac{3}{5} < \frac{5}{8} < \frac{2}{3} < \frac{5}{7} < \frac{3}{4} < \frac{4}{5} < \frac{5}{6} < \frac{6}{7} < \frac{1}{1}) .$$

The fractions in the above-mentioned Farey (sub)sequence are indexed starting with zero.

In Theorem 5 of this note we establish the connection between the standard Farey sequence \mathcal{F}_m and the halfsequences of $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$.

2. The Farey Subsequence $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), m)$

Recall that the map $\mathcal{F}_n \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_n$, which sends a fraction $\frac{h}{k}$ to $\frac{k-h}{k}$, is order-reversing and bijective. The sequences $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), m)$ and $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), n - m)$ have an analogous property:

Lemma 1 [7] *The map*

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), m) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), n - m) , \quad \frac{h}{k} \mapsto \frac{k-h}{k} , \tag{2}$$

is order-reversing and bijective.

If we write the fractions $\frac{h}{k} \in \mathbb{Q}$ as the column vectors $[\frac{h}{k}] \in \mathbb{Z}^2$, then map (2) can be thought of as the map

$$[\frac{h}{k}] \mapsto \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot [\frac{h}{k}] .$$

Let $a' \in \mathbb{B}(n)$ and $0 < m := \rho(a') < n$, where $\rho(a')$ denotes the poset rank of a' in $\mathbb{B}(n)$. For a subset $A \subset \mathbb{B}(n)$, let $\mathfrak{I}(A)$ and $\mathfrak{F}(A)$ denote the order ideal and filter in $\mathbb{B}(n)$, generated by A , respectively. The subposet $\mathfrak{F}(\mathfrak{I}(a') \cap \mathbb{B}(n)^{(1)})$, of cardinality $2^n - 2^{n-m}$, can be partitioned in the following way:

$$\mathfrak{F}(\mathfrak{I}(a') \cap \mathbb{B}(n)^{(1)}) = (\mathfrak{I}(a') - \{\hat{0}\}) \dot{\cup} \bigcup_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), m): \\ \frac{0}{1} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{1}}} \bigcup_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \min\{\frac{m}{h}, \frac{n-m}{k-h}\} \rfloor} (\mathbb{B}(n)^{(s \cdot k)} \cap (\mathfrak{F}(\mathfrak{I}(a') \cap \mathbb{B}(n)^{(s \cdot h)}) - \mathfrak{F}(\mathfrak{I}(a') \cap \mathbb{B}(n)^{(s \cdot h + 1)}))) ,$$

where $|\mathbb{B}(n)^{(s \cdot k)} \cap (\mathfrak{F}(\mathfrak{I}(a') \cap \mathbb{B}(n)^{(s \cdot h)}) - \mathfrak{F}(\mathfrak{I}(a') \cap \mathbb{B}(n)^{(s \cdot h + 1)}))| = \binom{m}{s \cdot h} \binom{n-m}{s \cdot (k-h)} .$

Since $|\mathcal{J}(a') - \{\hat{0}\}| = 2^m - 1$, we obtain

$$2^n - 2^{n-m} = 2^m - 1 + \sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), m): \\ \frac{0}{1} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{1}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \min\{\frac{m}{h}, \frac{n-m}{k-h}\} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot h} \binom{n-m}{s \cdot (k-h)} .$$

If $a'' \in \mathbb{B}(n)$ and $\rho(a'') = n - m$, then Lemma 1 implies

$$2^n - 2^m = 2^{n-m} - 1 + \sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), n-m): \\ \frac{0}{1} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{1}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \min\{\frac{n-m}{h}, \frac{m}{k-h}\} \rfloor} \binom{n-m}{s \cdot h} \binom{m}{s \cdot (k-h)} ,$$

and we come to the following conclusion:

Proposition 2 *Fractions from the Farey subsequences $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), m)$ and $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), n - m)$ satisfy the equality:*

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), m): \\ \frac{0}{1} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{1}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \min\{\frac{m}{h}, \frac{n-m}{k-h}\} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot h} \binom{n-m}{s \cdot (k-h)} \\ = & \sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(n), n-m): \\ \frac{0}{1} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{1}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \min\{\frac{n-m}{h}, \frac{m}{k-h}\} \rfloor} \binom{n-m}{s \cdot h} \binom{m}{s \cdot (k-h)} \\ = & 2^n - 2^m - 2^{n-m} + 1 . \end{aligned}$$

3. The Farey Subsequence $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$

Denote the left and right halfsequences of $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$ by

$$\mathcal{F}^{\leq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) := (f \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) : f \leq \frac{1}{2})$$

and

$$\mathcal{F}^{\geq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) := (f \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) : f \geq \frac{1}{2}) ,$$

respectively.

Lemma 3 [6] *The maps*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) & \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) , & \frac{h}{k} & \mapsto \frac{k-h}{k} , & \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix} & \mapsto \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix} , \\ \mathcal{F}^{\leq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) & \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^{\leq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) , & \frac{h}{k} & \mapsto \frac{k-2h}{2k-3h} , & \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix} & \mapsto \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 1 \\ -3 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix} , \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\mathcal{F}^{\geq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^{\geq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m), \quad \frac{h}{k} \mapsto \frac{h}{3h-k}, \quad \left[\begin{matrix} h \\ k \end{matrix} \right] \mapsto \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 3 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \left[\begin{matrix} h \\ k \end{matrix} \right],$$

are order-reversing and bijective.

Corollary 4 *The maps*

$$\mathcal{F}^{\leq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^{\geq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m), \quad \frac{h}{k} \mapsto \frac{k-h}{2k-3h}, \quad \left[\begin{matrix} h \\ k \end{matrix} \right] \mapsto \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ -3 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \left[\begin{matrix} h \\ k \end{matrix} \right],$$

and

$$\mathcal{F}^{\geq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^{\leq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m), \quad \frac{h}{k} \mapsto \frac{2h-k}{3h-k}, \quad \left[\begin{matrix} h \\ k \end{matrix} \right] \mapsto \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 \\ 3 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \left[\begin{matrix} h \\ k \end{matrix} \right],$$

are order-preserving and bijective.

Let $f_{t_3^1}, f_{t_2^1}, f_{t_3^2}, f_{t_1^1} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$, $m > 1$, where

$$f_{t_3^1} := \frac{1}{3}, \quad f_{t_2^1} := \frac{1}{2}, \quad f_{t_3^2} := \frac{2}{3}, \quad f_{t_1^1} := \frac{1}{1};$$

then Lemma 3 and Corollary 4 imply that $t_2^1 = 2t_3^1$, $t_3^2 = 3t_3^1$, and $t_1^1 = 4t_3^1$. This in particular means that the number $|\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)| - 1 =: t_1^1$ is divisible by four.

4. The Farey Sequence \mathcal{F}_m and the Farey Subsequence $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$

Let h be a positive integer, and $[i, l] := \{j : i \leq j \leq l\}$ an interval of positive integers. Let

$$\phi(h; [i, l]) := |\{j \in [i, l] : \gcd(h, j) = 1\}|;$$

thus, $\phi(h; [1, h])$ is the *Euler ϕ -function*. Recall that for a nonempty interval of positive integers $[i' + 1, i'']$ it holds $\phi(h; [i' + 1, i'']) = \sum_{d \in [1, \min\{i'', h\}]: d|h} \bar{\mu}(d) \cdot (\lfloor \frac{i''}{d} \rfloor - \lfloor \frac{i'}{d} \rfloor)$, where $d|h$ means that d divides h , and $\bar{\mu}(\cdot)$ stands for the *Möbius function*: $\bar{\mu}(1) := 1$; if $p^2|d$, for some prime p , then $\bar{\mu}(d) := 0$; if $d = p_1 p_2 \cdots p_s$ is the product of distinct primes p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s , then $\bar{\mu}(d) := (-1)^s$.

Let m be an integer, $m > 1$. For every integer h , $1 \leq h \leq m$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\{ \frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) : \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{2} \}| &= \phi(h; [2h + 1, h + m]) \\ &= \sum_{d \in [1, h]: d|h} \bar{\mu}(d) \cdot (\lfloor \frac{h+m}{d} \rfloor - \frac{2h}{d}) = \sum_{d \in [1, h]: d|h} \bar{\mu}(d) \cdot (\lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor - \frac{h}{d}) \\ &= \phi(h; [h + 1, m]) = |\{ \frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}_m : \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{1} \}|; \end{aligned}$$

hence, the sequences $\mathcal{F}^{\leq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$ and \mathcal{F}_m are of the same cardinality. Noticing that fractions $\frac{h_j}{k_j}$ and $\frac{h_{j+1}}{k_{j+1}}$ are consecutive in \mathcal{F}_m if and only if the fractions $\frac{h_j}{k_j+h_j}$ and $\frac{h_{j+1}}{k_{j+1}+h_{j+1}}$ are consecutive in $\mathcal{F}^{\leq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$, we arrive, with the help of Lemma 3 and Corollary 4, at the following conclusion:

Theorem 5 *Let m be an integer, $m > 1$. The maps*

$$\mathcal{F}^{\leq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_m, \quad \frac{h}{k} \mapsto \frac{h}{k-h}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix} \mapsto \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix},$$

and

$$\mathcal{F}_m \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^{\leq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m), \quad \frac{h}{k} \mapsto \frac{h}{k+h}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix} \mapsto \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix},$$

are order-preserving and bijective; the maps

$$\mathcal{F}^{\geq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_m, \quad \frac{h}{k} \mapsto \frac{k-h}{h}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix} \mapsto \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix},$$

and

$$\mathcal{F}_m \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^{\geq \frac{1}{2}}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m), \quad \frac{h}{k} \mapsto \frac{k}{k+h}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix} \mapsto \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} h \\ k \end{bmatrix},$$

are order-reversing and bijective.

Direct counting gives $|\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2), 1)| = 3$ and $|\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(4), 2)| = 5$.

Since $|\mathcal{F}_m| - 1 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{d \geq 1} \bar{\mu}(d) \cdot \lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor \cdot \lfloor \frac{m}{d} + 1 \rfloor$ (see, e.g., [4, §4.9]), Theorem 5 implies that for $m > 1$ we have

$$|\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)| - 1 = \sum_{d \geq 1} \bar{\mu}(d) \cdot \lfloor \frac{m}{d} \rfloor \cdot \lfloor \frac{m}{d} + 1 \rfloor.$$

By means of Theorem 5, the descriptions of sequences \mathcal{F}_m and $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$ supplement each other. For example, consider a fraction $\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}_m - \{\frac{0}{1}, \frac{1}{1}\}$. If x_0 is the integer such that $hx_0 \equiv -1 \pmod{k}$ and $m - k + 1 \leq x_0 \leq m$, then it is known (see, e.g., [2, §27.1]) that the fraction $\frac{hx_0+1}{k} / x_0$ succeeds the fraction $\frac{h}{k}$ in \mathcal{F}_m . Similarly, if x_0 is the integer such that $hx_0 \equiv 1 \pmod{k}$ and $m - k + 1 \leq x_0 \leq m$, then the fraction $\frac{hx_0-1}{k} / x_0$ precedes $\frac{h}{k}$ in \mathcal{F}_m . Theorem 5 leads to an analogous statement:

Remark 6 *Let m be an integer, $m > 1$.*

- (i) *Let $\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$. Suppose that $\frac{0}{1} < \frac{h}{k} \leq \frac{1}{2}$. Let x_0 be the integer such that $hx_0 \equiv 1 \pmod{(k-h)}$ and $m - k + h + 1 \leq x_0 \leq m$. The fraction $\frac{hx_0-1}{k-h} / \frac{kx_0-1}{k-h}$ precedes $\frac{h}{k}$ in $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$.*
- (ii) *Let $\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$. Suppose that $\frac{0}{1} \leq \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{2}$. Let x_0 be the integer such that $hx_0 \equiv -1 \pmod{(k-h)}$ and $m - k + h + 1 \leq x_0 \leq m$. The fraction $\frac{hx_0+1}{k-h} / \frac{kx_0+1}{k-h}$ succeeds $\frac{h}{k}$ in $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$.*

Proposition 2 can be reformulated in the case where $n := 2m$, with the help of the bijections mentioned in Lemma 3 and Corollary 4, in several ways which we now summarize:

Proposition 7 *Let m be an integer, $m > 1$. The following combinatorial identities hold for fractions from the Farey subsequence $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$:*

(i)

$$\sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m): \\ \frac{0}{1} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{1}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \min\{\frac{m}{h}, \frac{m}{k-h}\} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot h} \binom{m}{s \cdot (k-h)} = 2^{2m} - 2^{m+1} + 1 .$$

(ii)

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m): \\ \frac{0}{1} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{k-h} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot h} \binom{m}{s \cdot (k-h)} &= \sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m): \\ \frac{1}{2} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{1}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{h} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot h} \binom{m}{s \cdot (k-h)} \\ &= 2^{2m-1} - 2^m - \frac{1}{2} \binom{2m}{m} + 1 . \end{aligned}$$

(iii)

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m): \\ \frac{0}{1} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{k-h} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot (k-h)} \left(\binom{m}{s \cdot h} + \binom{m}{s \cdot (k-2h)} \right) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m): \\ \frac{1}{3} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{k-h} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot (k-h)} \left(\binom{m}{s \cdot h} + \binom{m}{s \cdot (k-2h)} \right) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m): \\ \frac{1}{2} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{2}{3}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{h} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot h} \left(\binom{m}{s \cdot (k-h)} + \binom{m}{s \cdot (2h-k)} \right) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m): \\ \frac{2}{3} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{1}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{h} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot h} \left(\binom{m}{s \cdot (k-h)} + \binom{m}{s \cdot (2h-k)} \right) \\ &= 2^{2m-1} - 2^m - \frac{1}{2} \binom{2m}{m} - \sum_{1 \leq t \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \binom{m}{2t} \binom{m}{t} + 1 . \end{aligned}$$

The bijections between the Farey sequence \mathcal{F}_m and the halfsequences of $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$, presented in Theorem 5, allow us to describe the properties of fractions from \mathcal{F}_m , analogous to those of fractions from $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{B}(2m), m)$, presented in Proposition 7(ii,iii):

Corollary 8 *Let m be an integer, $m > 1$. The following combinatorial identities hold for fractions from the standard Farey sequence \mathcal{F}_m :*

(i)

$$\sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}_m: \\ \frac{0}{1} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{1}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{k} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot h} \binom{m}{s \cdot k} = 2^{2m-1} - 2^m - \frac{1}{2} \binom{2m}{m} + 1 .$$

(ii)

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}_m: \\ \frac{0}{1} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{k} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot k} \left(\binom{m}{s \cdot h} + \binom{m}{s \cdot (k-h)} \right) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{\frac{h}{k} \in \mathcal{F}_m: \\ \frac{1}{2} < \frac{h}{k} < \frac{1}{1}}} \sum_{1 \leq s \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{k} \rfloor} \binom{m}{s \cdot k} \left(\binom{m}{s \cdot h} + \binom{m}{s \cdot (k-h)} \right) \\ &= 2^{2m-1} - 2^m - \frac{1}{2} \binom{2m}{m} - \sum_{1 \leq t \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \binom{m}{2t} \binom{m}{t} + 1 . \end{aligned}$$

References

- [1] D. Acketa and J. Žunić, *On the number of linear partitions of the (m, n) -grid*, Inform. Process. Lett. **38** (1991), no. 3, 163–168.
- [2] A.A. Buchstab, *Teoriya Chisel* (in Russian) [*Number Theory*], Uchpedgiz, Moscow, 1960.
- [3] S.B. Gashkov and V.N. Chubarikov, *Arifmetika. Algoritmy. Slozhnost' Vychisleniy, Third edition* (in Russian) [*Arithmetic. Algorithms. Complexity of Computation*], Drofa, Moscow, 2005.
- [4] R.L. Graham, D.E. Knuth and O. Patashnik, *Concrete Mathematics. A Foundation for Computer Science, Second edition*, Addison-Wesley, Reading Massachusetts, 1994.
- [5] G.H. Hardy and E.M. Wright, *An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers, Fifth edition*, Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1979.
- [6] A.O. Matveev, *Pattern recognition on oriented matroids: Layers of tope committees*, arXiv:math.CO/0612369.
- [7] A.O. Matveev, *Relative blocking in posets*, J. Comb. Optim. **13** (2007), no. 4, 379–403.
- [8] I. Niven, H.S. Zuckerman and H.L. Montgomery, *An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers, Fifth edition*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1991.
- [9] J.J. Tattersall, *Elementary Number Theory in Nine Chapters, Second edition*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2005.